

Dust in Galaxy Clusters: Modeling at Millimeter Wavelengths and Impact on Planck Cluster Cosmology

Jean-Baptiste Melin
CEA Saclay, France

***Collaborators:* J. Bartlett, Z.-Y. Cai, G. De Zotti,
J. Delabrouille, M. Roman, A. Bonaldi**

Outline

- Dust in clusters at crossroads between Astrophysics and Cosmology
- Modeling dust in clusters
- Implication for Planck cluster science

Dust in clusters and Astrophysics

Planck SZ “stacks” of ~260,000 Locally Brightest Galaxies @ $z \sim 0.1$ (SDSS)

Stellar mass

$$M_* \sim 2 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$$
$$M_{500} \sim 2 \times 10^{13} M_\odot$$

Planck Intermediate XI 2013

Dust in clusters and Astrophysics

Planck SZ “stacks” of $\sim 260,000$ Locally Brightest Galaxies @ $z \sim 0.1$ (SDSS)

Standard SZ Matched Multi-Filter
biased at low mass \rightarrow *dust!*

$\log_{10}(M_* [M_\odot])$
Stellar mass

Dust in clusters and Astrophysics

Planck SZ “stacks” of $\sim 300,000$ quasars $0.1 < z < 5$ (BOSS)

Dust in clusters

Astrophysics (at mm wavelengths)

- Dust dominates over SZ emission for halos $M_{500} < 2 \times 10^{13} M_{\odot}$ (@z=0.1)
- Dust: major emission of the quasars (@all z)

Traces SFR

Constrains stellar feedback in the IGM

Dust in clusters and Cosmology

How to reconcile Planck CMB and SZ counts?

- Primary CMB?
- Cluster mass calibration?

How to reconcile Planck CMB and SZ counts?

- Primary CMB?
- Cluster mass calibration?
- Selection function of SZ surveys? Dust ?
- New physics? Neutrino mass?
- Baryonic effects in the mass function?

Dust in clusters

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Cosmology (at mm wavelengths)

- Dust may impact SZ size and flux estimation
- Dust may have some impact on SZ survey completeness

Need to assess the impact on science results of SZ experiments!

Dust in clusters

Astrophysics (at mm wavelengths)

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Planck!

Dust in clusters: previous work

Planck cluster stacks vs. frequency

Frequency [GHz]

Planck Results XXIII 2015

Frequency [GHz]

Planck Intermediate XLIII 2016

see also H. Bourdin's talk

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The De Zotti et al. 2016 dust model

De Zotti et al. 2016
arXiv:1609.07263

Model based on Herschel data of field and cluster galaxies
(Alberts et al. 2014, 2016) and on spectral energy distributions from Cai. et al. 2013

No information on spatial distribution & no cross-check with Planck 857GHz

PSZ2 distribution and De Zotti et al. model ($0 < z < 1$)

Melin et al. in prep.

Dust in clusters: Planck data

Melin et al. in prep.

PSZ2 stacked profile
@ 857GHz

PSZ2 average matched filter flux

Dust in clusters: best fits

Melin et al. in prep.

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Dust in clusters: impact on cluster size recovery

Melin et al. in prep.

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Dust in clusters: impact on cluster flux recovery

Melin et al. in prep.

Very small effect: ~2% bias low for SZ flux $< 10^{-3}$ arcmin²

Dust in clusters: impact on survey completeness

Melin et al. in prep.

Maximum: $\sim < 9\%$ loss in $[0.5, 0.8]$

Planck cluster cosmology 2015

Melin et al. in prep.

Negligible shifts in cosmological parameters
Does not help to reconcile low-z and high-z counts

Conclusions

- **Dust model based on De Zotti et al. 2016 and Planck 857GHz** (normalization of $L_{\text{IR}}\text{-M}$ and profile)
- Only **small impact on individual cluster flux** ($\sim < 2\%$) and negligible impact on cluster size estimation
- **Planck size overestimation not due to dust.** Most probably due to profile mismatch between the Matched Multi-Filter and cluster profiles
- **Small impact on survey completeness** ($\sim < 9\%$ for z in $[0.5-0.8]$) and **negligible shifts of cosmological parameters**
- SZ future (e.g. **CMB-S4**): **dust will matter.** Crucial to look at the impact on SZ science (will depend on resolution, sensitivity, frequency coverage)

Backup slides

The SZ Matched Multi-Filter (MMF)

 **Minimum variance
and unbiased SZ flux**

The SZ Matched Multi-Filter (MMF)

BIAS if other emissions

➔ Minimum variance
and unbiased SZ flux... if cluster emission is SZ only

↑

Selection function of SZ surveys?

Planck cluster stacks vs. frequency

Frequency [GHz]

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